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Ethics in Medicine

Why early treating hidradenitis suppurativa is also a moral issue.

Abstract

Hidradenitis suppurativa is a multifactorial, often autoimmune, chronic inflammatory disease of terminal follicles in skin envelope folds that can lead to marked scarring and disability and has a high disease burden. It manifests with very painful, deeply localized, sterile inflammatory skin nodules over sub-dermal caverns occurring in terminal follicle and apocrine gland-rich skin regions, most commonly in the axillae and inguinal, lower back and anogenital regions. The most common complication is superinfection with infectious agents. Our study group has tried to clarify the question of whether it makes economic sense to treat this disease, which is not so rare, free of charge, even in countries without general health insurance.

Hidradenitis suppurativa

Despite intensified research in recent years, the pathogenesis of hidradenitis suppurativa is still unclear. In particular, the reason for the chronicity of the disease is still unclear or disputed. The natural course of the disease in different degrees of severity and the accompanying provoking factors are only partially known. However, the ideas about the pathogenesis

of hidradenitis suppurativa have changed significantly in the last decades. There are many indications that the primary changes do not affect the apocrine glands, as originally assumed, but mostly terminal hair follicles. The central pathogenetic event is a hyperkeratosis with occlusion of the upper part of the hair follicle comparable to acne vulgaris and not a suppurative inflammation of the apocrine sweat glands. Obviously, a perifollicular

lymphocytic inflammation and usually a likewise very early infundibular epithelial hyperplasia are the basis of the following sinus formations. If one follows this approach, both established names of the disease, namely hidradenitis suppurativa or acne inversa, would be considered misnomers. In contrast to acne vulgaris, however, an overproduction of sebum or its altered composition does not seem to be a significant factor. Subsequent dilatation can lead to rupture of the follicle with subsequent purulent inflammatory reaction and scarring in the dermis, resulting in sinus formation. After severe tissue damage has subsided, free hair shafts surrounded by an inflammatory infiltrate can also be detected, often as the only indicator that the process originated from the hair follicle. In contrast, other authors suggest that the apocrine glands nevertheless play a role in the hidradenitis suppurativa manifestation, namely that apocrine glands have an effect on the acro-infundibulum through the secretion of a yet unknown factor. The recognized trigger factors of hidradenitis suppurativa include autoimmune processes, metabolic disorders (e.g. hemochromatosis, H63D syndrome, metabolic syndrome), oxidative stress (also the type triggered by smoking), possibly also genetic predisposition, regional hyperhidrosis and profound mechanical irritation. An accumulation of diseases of the atopic circle and inflammatory bowel diseases in patients with hidradenitis suppurativa could not be proven, even though a comorbidity of inflammatory bowel diseases and hidradenitis suppurativa has been reported in older studies.^{7,13}

Inflammatory processes

Hidradenitis suppurativa is a disease of the terminal hair follicles associated with lympho-histiocytic inflammation,

granulomatous reactions, and the formation of sinus tracts and scars, and the deep areas of the follicles seem to be particularly involved. Histological studies of hidradenitis suppurativa report follicular occlusion, attributed to hyperkeratosis. Irrespective of the duration of the disease, inflammation and possible secondary infections occur as a result of the occlusion of the apocrine glands and subsequent rupture of the follicles. An expression of the cytokines IL-1 β , CXCL9 (MIG), IL-10, IL-11, BLC and IL-17A and a decrease in the expression of IL-20 and IL-22 were detected in skin lesions of patients with hidradenitis suppurativa. The IL-23/Th17 pathway is stimulated in hidradenitis suppurativa.¹¹

Hidradenitis suppurativa is explicitly not a primarily bacterial infectious disease of the skin. It has become the current state of scientific knowledge that hidradenitis suppurativa is no longer classified as a pyoderma.¹¹ Nevertheless, a large number of gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria have been detected in hair follicles of the affected region, most frequently *S. aureus*, *Peptostreptococcus* species, *Propionibacterium acnes* as well as *E. coli*, *Proteus* and other pathogens. In patients with hidradenitis suppurativa, a reduced response of monocytes to bacterial components was observed over time. Compared to normal skin, the number of Toll-like receptor (TLR)-2-expressing infiltrating macrophages (CD68+) and dermal dendrocytes (CD209+) increased in hidradenitis suppurativa lesions. TLR-2 are stimulated by bacterial products and have a pro-inflammatory effect. To what extent the stimulation of TLR plays a causal role in hidradenitis suppurativa, or if these findings are an epiphenomenon, must be shown in further studies.^{12,15} It is assumed that changes in the defence against bacterial infections may occur, e.g.

through an attenuated response of monocytes to inflammatory stimuli. Furthermore, altered expression of antimicrobial peptides was found, such as over-expression of psoriasin in the lower layers of the epidermis, whereas the expression level of human β -defensin-2 (hBD-2) was reduced in the epidermis. In the sub-epidermal dermis, however, in contrast to normal skin, hBD-2-expressing monocytes/macrophages were also found. An increased expression of tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α and the proven activation of TLR receptors could be responsible for this. The increased expression of C-type lectin receptors, which play a role in antigen presentation by macrophages and dendrites, suggests an interaction of TLR with C-type lectin receptors as a trigger of chronic inflammation in hidradenitis suppurativa.^{14,15,16,17}

Clinical aspects

Hidradenitis suppurativa is associated with lesions, some of which are very painful when pressure is applied, and deep subcutaneous nodules that either⁸

- regress spontaneously
- persist
- coalesce subcutaneously into a network of cavities with sinusoidal ducts
- or transform into an infected abscess

Horizontal involvement of the entire dermis and the formation of sub-dermal caverns, usually filled with serous, sticky or even creamy blood, are typical. If bacterial complications occur, abscess formation is also possible.⁷ Rupture to the outside is rare; foci are more likely to form.^{9,10}

If spontaneous ruptures occur, it is usually due to abscess formation, which can be recognized by typical abscess symptoms and purulent discharge.

Hidradenitis suppurativa is not acne: the deep areas of the follicles seem to be affected and not the acroinfundibulum as in acne vulgaris, where the convex skin surfaces are affected. For this reason, unlike acne vulgaris, closed comedones are not found, but follicular papules and pustules may develop both in the early stages and later. Initially, the inflammatory lesions are transient, but gradually become chronic. Large, sometimes livid erythematous, nodular, honeycombed areas with abscesses and fistula-like ducts form, accompanied by significant fibrosis (hypertrophic scarring) and further nodulation. Fistula formation may also occur in the anal region. Spontaneous healing is not expected. Horizontal spread of the disease remains essentially localized in the dermis.^{8,9}

Treatment

Any undiagnosed or misdiagnosed hidradenitis suppurativa, both limited and multiloculated, carries a risk of dangerous bacterial abscesses or, in the long term, squamous cell carcinoma due to the persistent inflammatory situation.⁹ As with many diseases, early treatment is critical.⁶ The longer a patient delays seeing a dermatologist or the later a physician realizes that he or she is being misled by nonspecific initial symptoms, the more difficult it becomes to treat the disease, which in advanced stages often requires expensive and potentially serious surgical removal of large areas of skin. In the early stages, aggressive treatment is critical and, more importantly, helpful:^{8,9,10}

- steroid injections with triamcinolone directly into the nodule
- incision and drainage (I&D), often multiple times
- topical and/or oral antibiotics
- reduction of intra-lesional pressure

Steroid injections and the incision method in particular are thought to work in a counterintuitive manner in nonbacterial (sterile) nodules (that is <3-4 inches). Both the injections and the incision through all layers of skin deep into the underlying cavern are definitely helpful directly, but they are also helpful indirectly by signaling the immune system that there is inflammation or wounding (depending on the technique used) that requires primary wound healing.¹³ The hypothesis that this trigger may change the immune system's "perception" of the nodule is justified. A switch from fighting a nonexistent threat (autoimmunity) to registering an open wound that needs to heal from within can apparently be induced by this type of early treatment. Based on the available data, this postulated double-strike therapy is as promising as it appears to be permanent. This, of course, applies only to sterile nodules with non-purulent sub-dermal caverns. Infected nodules must be treated with appropriately high doses of oral antibiotics and removed by extensive surgery in sano. Given the low cost and good prognosis of very early incision and drainage (often more than once) plus ointment dressings with 40% tetracycline, 40% mometasone, and 10% topical heparin for 7-21 days, any delay in treatment cannot be justified. Topical heparin at the strength of 80,000 to 120,000 I.U. facilitates drainage of serous blood from the subcutaneous caverns after a sufficiently long, wide, and deep incision.

Moral aspects

If left untreated, hidradenitis suppurativa develops into a difficult-to-treat and chronic disease. Not only do the chances of complete cure of the disease decrease with each day, but the cost of complex treatment of advanced hidradenitis suppurativa skyrockets with each day

wasted. Many patients become so ill that they have to give up their jobs, become welfare cases, and may even die from an abscess. None of this would be necessary if the general public knew how to recognize hidradenitis nodules and that early treatment is possible, effective and very cheap. Rarely is a skin disease (or skin symptom of a systemic disease) as rather easily and inexpensively treated at the outset as hidradenitis suppurativa - and as problematic and expensive in advanced stages. Therefore, it is unjustifiable for dermatologists to charge uninsured or underinsured patients extortionate prices for a treatment that any well-trained nurse can perform. Knowing what a serious disease hidradenitis suppurativa can develop into, it should be a moral obligation for every surgeon and dermatologist to offer early treatment for this disease not only at an affordable fee but basically free of charge for those in need.⁶

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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